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FOREIGN INVESTMENT, FOREIGN TRADE AND GROWTH NEXUS IN BANGLADESH: A MULTIVARIATE COINTEGRATION ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT.

Export, import and foreign direct investment (FDI) play important role in economic development and growth. This paper investigates the direction of causal link among export, import, foreign direct investment and economic growth measured in GDP. The paper uses a theoretically reliable technique to investigate legitimacy of the export led growth (ELG) hypothesis for Bangladesh considering the variable import as well and also seek relation between FDI and economic growth. The paper investigates the Granger-causality test among exports, imports, FDI, and economic growth in Bangladesh over the period 1980-2011 as well as the modern cointegration test also. What we find is no long run relation exists among the variables. And there is one way causal relation from export to GDP but GDP to FDI.

I. Introduction

There are some issues in the literature of development economics which have long been debated and have not been resolved yet. The causal link of export, import and foreign direct investment (FDI) with economic growth is one of them. There are findings which support that FDI tends to endorse economic growth. By providing new production procedure, techniques, administrative skills, capital goods, FDI promotes economic growth of the less developed countries (LDC) or the so called third world countries. The rationale for increased efforts to magnetize more FDI stems from the faith that FDI has several positive effects. Again, others found that FDI follow economic growth. Economic growth first provides necessary and conducive economic factors for FDI to play a positive role for economic development.

On the other hand, Export-led growth (ELG) is an economic development approach in which export and foreign trade in broad play a vital role in a country's economic growth and development. There has been a wide-ranging comprehensive swing towards the ELG tactic in recent years. This change has been found to be due to the actual and potential economic benefits this strategy accords to both developing and developed countries in a similar way. Export growth is said to result in augmented output, employment and consumption, all of which lead to a boost in the demand for a country's output (Jung and Marshall, 1985). Besides, a strong export sector enlarges the domestic market so that firms achieve economies of scale and thus lower unit costs. This may be likely because an export sector allows a country to trade along its lines of comparative advantage, (Tyler, 1981:127). This in the main leads to efficient resource distribution.

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This efficiency forces firms to implement modern know-how and bring into being quality products that congregate the demands of stylish consumers in global markets (Mayer, 1995).

Besides, trade may also help a country with positive export externality which leads economic growth (Bradford, 1994; Feder, 1983; and Sengupta and Espana, 1994). Moreover, trade may facilitate a developing country to overcome the ax-ante saving-investment gap and the ax-ante import-export gap (Chenery and Strout 1966 ;).

These reimbursement of the ELG strategy have led, not only to the adoption of this strategy by many countries, but also to a burgeoning of many studies to test the pragmatic legitimacy of the premise (see Shan and Sun, 1998; Marin, 1992; and Islam, 1998; Ghatak, Milner and Utkulu, 1997; Ghatak and Price 1997; and Ukpolo, 1994). Nonetheless, there are still questions as to whether the ELG tactic will also be advantageous to the small resource-based economy of Bangladesh. The paper will focus this question.

Issues such as whether FDI causes economic growth and what is the causal direction between economic growth and FDI are not resolved. The same goes for export and import. There are still questions as to whether export or import causes growth or growth causes export or import. such an important and unsolved issue deserves further investigation. This paper aims to examine the causal link between FDI and economic growth as well as export or import and economic growth in the context of South-Asian country Bangladesh. An investigation of causal link among export, import, FDI and economic growth has strategic and policy implications for developing economics like Bangladesh. Specifically, the objective of this paper is to assess whether export revenues and FDI can lead to noteworthy economic growth in a country like Bangladesh. To achieve this, the paper uses time series econometric analysis to test the causal relationship

The sketch of this paper is as follows: after introducing issues in section I, section II provides literature review, while section III and IV postulates the data and theoretical framework respectively. The methodology is presented in section V and the empirical results are reported in section VI. Finally section VII provides the summary and conclusion of the present study.

II. Review of Literature

Basically the literature on the role of export as well as import two of the deterministic factors of economic growth is a very aged perception. Both Adam Smith and David Ricardo argued in favor of global trade as an important factor of economic expansion. The ELG paradigm has received a lot of attention following the highly successful East Asian export-led growth strategy during the 1970s and 1980s, and especially because of the overall breakdown of import substitution policies in most of African and Latin American countries.

Export growth helps in better utilization of the resources leading to total increase in factor productivity. This hypothesis is in essence studied for the developing and the less developing nations. Authors like Balassa (1978 and 1985), Jung and Marshall (1985), Ram (1985), Chow (1987), Bahmani-Oskoe, Mohtadi and Shabsigh (1991), Bahmani-Oskoe and Alse (1993), Levin and Raut (1997), and Khalifa Al-Youssif (1997) have focused on export led hypothesis and their contribution to economic growth. The exports has led to the advantages of economies of scale, increased capacity utilization, technology transfer etc. There are some the studies that exactly do not substantiate to the conclusions of export led hypothesis. Clarke and Kirkpatrick (1992) use pooled data for 80 developing countries from 1981-1988 to estimate the impact of trade policy reform on the economic performance and conclude that trade reform does not affect economic performance.

On the other hand, regarding the FDI issue we observe that during the last two decades a huge number of studies focused on the role of FDI in stimulating economic growth in the LDC. But there is no harmony with regard to the direction of causality. Hansen and Rand (2006) found strong causal link from FDI to GDP for developing countries during 1970-2000. Bloomstrom, Lipsey and Zejan (1996) found evidence that FDI causes economic growth. However, positive contribution of FDI is conditional. According to them, FDI is growth enhancing De Mello (1997) found that FDI had significantly positive effect on economic growth for the countries with high income.

Borensztein, Gregorio, and Lee (1998) found that FDI contributed economic growth to countries when the labor force has attained certain level of educational standard. Carkovic and Levine (2002) examined the effect of FDI on economic growth and concluded that FDI had no impact on long term economic growth. They argued that the lack of positive impact of FDI on economic growth is not conditional upon human capital, level of economic development or openness of the economy. Zhang (2001) examined 11 countries of Asia and South America and found no uniform pattern of direction with regard to FDI and economic growth. Zhang (2000) argued that economic growth lead to FDI growth. Rapid economic growth in the host country increases aggregate demand which stimulates higher demand for investments including FDI. Hermesand Lensink (2003) concluded that the development of financial system was an important factor for FDI to have a positive impact on economic growth. Caves (1996) found bidirectional relationship. FDI and economic growth are positively interdependent. Large economic growth provides high profit opportunities attracting higher domestic and foreign direct investments. On the other hand, FDI through its spill over effect have direct positive economic growth of the host countries. Chowdhry and Mavrotas (2006) found relationship of bidirectional causality between FDI and economic growth. Kholdy and Sohrabian (2005) found no causal link between FDI and economic growth. Thus, the empirical evidence on the causal link between FDI and economic growth is varied.

III. Data

The data set is annual, spanning 1980/81 through 2010/11. The dependent variable is the annualized real GDP, and the explanatory variables are the annual real export, import and FDI as well. To test if the series are nonstationary or contain a unit root, we focus on the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) test. We have used EViews 6 as statistical software package.

IV. Theoretical Background

The import substitution strategies ask for to endorse hasty industrialization of the home production to surrogate the imports required to advance economic maturity. Consequently, the government involves import trade barriers as import quotas, tariffs etc. On the other hand, outward-looking development (or export led growth) strategies involve strategies supporting manufacturing sectors. This structure argues that global trade promotes specialization in production of export products, which in turn boosts the efficiency stage (Helpman, Krugman, 1985, Boomstrom, 1986) and causes the general level of skills to mount in the export segment. Regarding the FDI issue we have already discussed some theoretical aspects at the very begging of our study. We do not want to make any repetition.

However to construct relation among the concerned variables i.e. export, import and growth, the following equation is considered to which constant and error term are incorporated.

$$Y_t = \alpha + \beta_1 X_t + \beta_2 M_t + \beta_3 FDI_t + \varepsilon_t \quad [1]$$

V. Estimation

5.1 Econometric Methodology

Transforming all the variables into natural log forms, finally our baseline equation is as follows which is just equation [1]:

$$\ln Y_t = \alpha + \ln \beta_1 X_t + \ln \beta_2 M_t + \ln \beta_3 FDI_t + \varepsilon_t \quad [2]$$

The equation was estimated as an OLS regression. The estimated coefficients of the baseline equation are reported in Table 1 in Appendix-3

5.2 Unit Autoregressive Root Tests

In order to scrutinize the stationarity properties of the data, a univariate analysis of each of the three time series (real GDP, real exports, and real imports) was carried out by testing for the presence of a unit root.

Augmented Dickey Fuller $\hat{Z}$ ADF, t-tests $\hat{Z}$ Dickey and Fuller, 1979 and Phillips and Perron (1988) $Z(t\hat{\alpha})$ -tests for the individual time series.

The null hypothesis of these tests is that series are non-stationary. The ADF tests assume that the error terms are statistically independent and have a constant variance. This assumption may not be true of all the data used, and so the Phillip-Perron test is used to relax the above assumptions and permit the error disturbances to be heterogeneously distributed.

5.2.1 Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test:

Said and dickey (1984) enhance the essential autoregressive unit root test to accommodate general ARMA(p, q) models with unidentified orders. Their test is known as the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test which is based on estimating the following regression:

$$y_t = \beta'D_t + \phi y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^p \psi_j \Delta y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad [3]$$

Where D_t is a vector of deterministic terms (constant, trend etc.) The ρ (lagged difference terms) and Δy_{t-j} are used to estimate the ARMA arrangement of the errors, and ρ value is set so that the error ε_t is successively uncorrelated. The error term is assumed to be homoskedastic. The extent of the deterministic terms depends on the implicit behavior of y_t under the alternative hypothesis of trend stationarity. Under the null hypothesis, y_t is I(1) which implies that $\phi = 1$. The ADF t-statistic and normalized prejudice statistic are based on the least squares estimates of (4.3) and are given by

$$ADF_t = t_{\phi-1} = \frac{\phi - 1}{SE(\phi)} \quad [4]$$

$$ADF_n = \frac{T(\hat{\phi} - 1)}{1 - \hat{\psi}_1 - \dots - \hat{\psi}_p} \quad [5]$$

$$\Delta y_t = \beta'D_t + \pi y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^p \psi_j \Delta y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad [6]$$

$\pi = \phi - 1$. Under the null hypothesis, Δy_t is I(0) which implies that $\pi = 0$. The ADF t-statistic is then the usual t-statistic for testing $\pi = 0$ and the ADF normalized

bias statistic is $T\hat{\pi}/(1-\hat{\psi}_1-\dots-\hat{\psi}_p)$. The test regression (4.4) is often used in practice because the ADF t-statistic is the usual t-statistic reported for testing the significance of the coefficient y_{t-1} . The *S+FinMetrics* function unitroot follows this convention.

5.2.2 The Phillips –Perron Test:

Phillips and Perron (1988) developed a number of unit root tests that have become fashionable in the analysis of monetary time series. The Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root tests vary from the ADF tests largely in how they deal with sequential correlation and heteroskedasticity in the errors. In particular, where the ADF tests use a parametric autoregression to estimate the ARMA arrangement of the errors in the test regression, the PP tests disregard any sequential correlation in the test regression. The test regression for the PP tests is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta y_t &= \beta D_t + \pi y_{t-1} + u_t \\ u_t &\approx I(0)\end{aligned}\quad [7]$$

Where u_t is $I(0)$ and may be heteroskedastic. The PP tests correct for any sequential (or serial) correlation and heteroskedasticity in the errors u_t of the test regression by directly modifying the test statistics $t_{\pi=0}$ and $T\hat{\pi}$. These modified statistics, denoted Z_t and Z_π are given by

$$Z_t = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\hat{\lambda}^2}\right)^{1/2} \cdot t_{\pi=0} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\hat{\lambda}^2 - \hat{\sigma}^2}{\hat{\lambda}^2}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{T \cdot SE(\hat{\pi})}{\hat{\sigma}^2}\right)$$

$$Z_\pi = T\hat{\pi} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{T^2 \cdot SE(\hat{\pi})}{\hat{\sigma}^2} (\hat{\lambda}^2 - \hat{\sigma}^2)$$

The terms $\hat{\sigma}^2$ and $\hat{\lambda}^2$ are consistent estimates of the variance parameters.

Under the null hypothesis that $\pi = 0 = 0$, the PP Z_t and Z_π statistics have the same asymptotic distributions as the ADF t-statistic and normalized bias statistics. One improvement of the PP tests over the ADF tests is that the PP tests are vigorous to broad forms of heteroskedasticity in the error term u_t . Another advantage is that the user does not have to identify a lag length for the test regression.

The result of the unit root test is displayed in appendices A3 at table 2 and 3 respectively.

5.3 Cointegration Test

Johansen Full-Information Maximum Likelihood Method

Although Engle-Granger (1987) first proposed cointegration techniques, there are some shortcomings in their methodology. First, Engle-Granger method gives deliberate choice of the endogenous variable to put on the left-hand side of the model. They also ignore the possibility of more than one cointegrating vector when more than two variables are included in the model. On the contrary, in the Johansen multivariate approach, all the variables are explicitly endogenous so that no arbitrary normalization has to be made without testing. Thus, the study also employed the Johansen cointegration test technique using Trace Statistic and Maximum Eigenvalue statistic.

The time series variables of our model (equation 2) for investigating the effect on growth, incorporated in this paper, is considered to follow the first order Vector Auto Regressive (VAR) representation defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \ln Y_{i,t} &= \Pi_{11} \ln Y_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{12} \ln X_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{13} \ln M_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{14} \ln FDI_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{\ln Y_{i,t}} \\
 \ln X_{i,t} &= \Pi_{21} \ln Y_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{22} \ln X_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{23} \ln M_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{24} \ln FDI_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{\ln X_{i,t}} \\
 \ln M_{i,t} &= \Pi_{31} \ln Y_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{32} \ln X_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{33} \ln M_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{34} \ln FDI_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{\ln M_{i,t}} \\
 \ln FDI_{i,t} &= \Pi_{41} \ln Y_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{42} \ln X_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{43} \ln M_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{44} \ln FDI_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{\ln FDI_{i,t}}
 \end{aligned} \quad [8]$$

Now, subtracting lagged dependent variables from equations [8], the following matrix notation can be constructed:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta \ln Y_{i,t} \\ \Delta \ln X_{i,t} \\ \Delta \ln M_{i,t} \\ \Delta \ln FDI_{i,t} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \Gamma_{11} & \Gamma_{12} & \Gamma_{13} & \Gamma_{14} \\ \Gamma_{21} & \Gamma_{22} & \Gamma_{23} & \Gamma_{24} \\ \Gamma_{31} & \Gamma_{32} & \Gamma_{33} & \Gamma_{34} \\ \Gamma_{41} & \Gamma_{42} & \Gamma_{43} & \Gamma_{44} \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \ln Y_{i,t} \\ \ln X_{i,t} \\ \ln M_{i,t} \\ \ln FDI_{i,t} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{\ln Y_{i,t}} \\ \varepsilon_{\ln X_{i,t}} \\ \varepsilon_{\ln M_{i,t}} \\ \varepsilon_{\ln FDI_{i,t}} \end{bmatrix} \quad \dots [9]$$

Where $\Gamma_{11} = \Pi_{11}I$, $\Gamma_{22} = \Pi_{22}I$, $\Gamma_{33} = \Pi_{33}I$, $\Gamma_{44} = \Pi_{44}I$, $\Gamma_{12} = \Pi_{12}$, $\Gamma_{13} = \Pi_{13}$, $\Gamma_{21} = \Pi_{21}$, $\Gamma_{23} = \Pi_{23}$, $\Gamma_{31} = \Pi_{31}$, $\Gamma_{32} = \Pi_{32}$, $\Gamma_{14} = \Pi_{14}$, $\Gamma_{24} = \Pi_{24}$, $\Gamma_{34} = \Pi_{34}$, $\Gamma_{44} = \Pi_{44}$ and $\ln Y_{it}$, $\ln X_{it}$, $\ln M_{it}$ and $\ln FDI_{it}$ are integrated of order one i.e., $I(1)$. Johansen recommends two different likelihood ratio tests of the significance of the canonical correlations and thereby the reduced rank of the matrix: the trace test and maximum eigen value test i.e.

$$\lambda_{\text{trace}(r)} = -T \sum_{i=r+1}^k \ln(1 - \hat{\lambda}_i)$$

$$\lambda_{\text{max}(r,r+1)} = -T \ln(1 - \hat{\lambda}_{r+1})$$

Here T is the sample size and $\hat{\lambda}_i$ is the i^{th} largest canonical association. The trace tests the null hypothesis of r cointegrating vectors against the alternative hypothesis of n cointegrating vectors. The maximum eigenvalue test, in contrast, tests the null hypothesis of r cointegrating vectors against the alternative hypothesis of $r+1$ cointegrating vectors. Asymptotic critical values can be got from Johansen and Juselius (1990).

5.4 Granger Causality

As mentioned earlier, the present study has adopted the Granger Causality Test to test the short-run nature and the direction of causality among annual real GDP, annual export and import in Bangladesh. The following bivariate Granger Causality model is estimated:

Causality between GDP and Export:

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_i X_{t-i} + u_t$$

$$X_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i X_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_i Y_{t-i} + v_t \quad [10]$$

Causality between GDP and Import:

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \delta_i M_{t-i} + u_t$$

$$M_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i M_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_i Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad [11]$$

Causality between FDI and GDP:

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_i FDI_{t-i} + u_t$$

$$FDI_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i FDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_i Y_{t-i} + v_t \quad [12]$$

The number of lagged terms to be introduced in the Granger Causality Test is an important practical question in the analysis. In the present study the above models were estimated up to eight lags to see the changes or variations in the results (if any). However, except a little bit no considerable changes and variations in the estimated different lag models were found. The results of pair wise Granger Causality Test conducted between GDP v/s Export (equation 10), GDP v/s Import (equation 11) and GDP v/s FDI (equation 12) is reported in Table 5.

I. Empirical Results

Table 1 in appendix A3 shows regression analysis of the considered variables. The coefficient on export is positively correlated with the growth rate. A one-percentage point increase in export is associated with a 0.3961 percentage point increase in growth. Import variable has negative sign. A one-percentage point increase of import is associated with a 0.2216 percentage point decrease in growth. That is import tends to affect our growth negatively. It has negative contribution on growth. This indirectly indicates the victory of export led growth. And surprisingly we see FDI has very little contribution on growth. A one-percentage point increase in FDI leads to 0.0307 percentage point increase in growth. Finally, R-Sq and R-Sq (adj) both show moderate values.

Tables 2 and 3 in appendix A4 shows the result of unit root test. Table 3 confirms that all the variables are stationary in the first differenced series i.e., $I(1)$ in all the cases. The results provide the basis for the test of long run relationship among the variables.

Table 4 in appendix A5 reports Johansen–Juselius Cointegration results Both the ‘trace statistic’ and ‘eigen value test’ leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis of $r = 0$ (no cointegrating vectors) against the alternative hypothesis $r > 0$ (one or more cointegrating vectors), the null of $r \leq 1$ against the alternative of $r > 2$ (two or more cointegrating vectors) while the null of $r \leq 2$ against the alternative of $r = 3$ (three or more cointegrating vectors) and the null of $r \leq 3$ against $r = 4$ against the alternative of $r = 3$ cannot be rejected at 5% and 1% level of significance. The results provide evidence that there is no cointegrating relationship among the variables in our model.

Table 5 in appendix A6 shows Pairwise Granger Causality Tests of the variables. At first stage (equation 10) we have done the causality between GDP and export. Up to two lags, there is feedback or bilateral causality between GDP and export. However starting from lags three to lag seven we get a new result but the same that is export causes GDP but GDP does not Granger causes export. But at eight lags, there is no statistically perceptible relationship between the two variables. This reinforces the point that the outcome of the Granger causality test is sensitive to the number of lags introduced

in the model. However our conclusion is export Granger causes GDP but GDP does not. And at second stage (equation 11) we have done the causality between GDP and import. At first lags there is feedback relation between GDP and import. But just after that up to lags seven both GDP and import are independent from each other i.e. no statistical visible relation exists. However at eight lags, we observe import causes GDP but GDP does not Granger cause import.

At third stage (equation 12) causality between GDP and FDI is shown. There is bilateral relation between GDP and FDI at lags one. At lags two we see GDP Granger causes FDI but FDI does not causes GDP. After that we get the same result up to lags seven i.e. GDP Granger causes FDI but not that FDI causes GDP. At lags eight the result is ambiguous. This again reminds us the point made earlier that the direction of causality critically depends on the number of lagged terms included in the model. So finally our conclusion is GDP causes FDI and FDI does not cause GDP.

VII. Summary and Conclusion

In the theoretical literature that has evolved during the last three decades, there has been greater focus on the critical role of export and import as important vehicle to speed up economic growth. Most economists have argued that opening up of economies is an effective strategy of achieving faster economic growth. It is asserted that export growth emanating from outward oriented economic policies leads to boost GDP growth. Also, there is potential for reverse causality, i.e. GDP growth leads to export growth. These issues are still debatable, and there is contradictory empirical evidence which rejects the hypothesis of such relationships between economic and export growth. Through the cointegration test we see that there exists no long run relation among the variables. However, the broad consensus among economists as well as among policy makers regarding GDP and export are that there is a close symbiotic relationship between GDP growth and export growth. The result of causality test suggests one way causality running from export to GDP. So what we think is that promoting exports via export promotion policies will contribute to economic growth in Bangladesh.

On the other hand, the results of the paper also suggest that we should weigh the cost of policies aimed at improving local conditions versus those that seek to attract FDI. Better local conditions not only magnetize foreign companies but also let host economies to maximize the benefits of foreign investments. Since we have already seen by the causality test that causal link runs from economic growth to FDI. If the causal link runs from economic growth to FDI, it means that economic growth is a prerequisite for attracting and captivating FDI. In such a case, the policy implication is that Bangladesh must lay emphasis on economic growth rather than going after FDI.

APPENDICES

A1. Data Sources:

All the data of the corresponding variables i.e. the real gdp, export and import are collected from the World Bank website that is from the World Development Indicator where the data is spanned from 1980 to 2011

A2. Definition of the Variables:

lnGDP = Ln of Bangladesh Real GDP. The Nominal GDP is deflated by the GDP Deflator.

lnX = Ln of Bangladesh Export in billion

lnM = Ln of Bangladesh Import in billion

lnFDI = Ln of Foreign Direct Investment

A3. Empirical Results:

Table 1: Regression Analysis

. regress lngr lnx lnm lnfdi

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs = 32		
Model	1.72945121	3	.576483737	F(3, 28) =	8.96	
Residual	1.80115064	28	.064326808	Prob > F	= 0.0003	
				R-squared	= 0.4898	
				Adj R-squared	= 0.4352	
Total	3.53060185	31	.113890382	Root MSE	= .25363	

lngr	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
lnx	.3961569	.2033416	1.95	0.061	-.0203695	.8126834
lnm	-.2216684	.3668558	-0.60	0.551	-.9731384	.5298015
lnfdi	.0307199	.0427206	0.72	0.478	-.0567894	.1182292
_cons	.7083433	.6250897	1.13	0.267	-.572095	1.988781

A4. Unit root Test:**Table 2: unit root test (NON-STATIONARITY)**

Variables	Lag	ADFAt Level		PPAt Level		Decision
		Intercept	Trend & Intercept	Intercept	Trend & Intercept	Order of Integration
LnGDP	1	-1.987	-4.317*	3.990***	-6.896***	I(0)
LnX	1	-0.80	-2.835	-0.296	-4.943***	I(0)
LnM	1	0.331	-2.199	0.151	-3.362**	I(0)
LnFDI	1	-0.807	-3.502**	-0.782	-3.476**	I(0)

Notes: 1) *denotes significance level at 5% and 10%; **denotes significance level at 10% While ***denotes significance level at 1%, 5% and 10%.

2) The test statistics value of PP test is based on Spectral estimation method-Bartlett Kernel and the Bandwidth is New-West Bandwidth automatic selection by the software itself.

Table 3: unit root test (stationary)

Variables	Lag	ADFAt First Difference		PPAt First Difference	Decision
		Intercept	Trend & Intercept		
LnGDP	1	-7.343***	-7.302***	-3.990***	I(1)
LnX	1	-6.547***	-6.425***	-0.296*	I(1)
LnM	1	-0.883***	-4.463**	-11.665***	I(1)
LnFDI	1	-5.341**	-5.362***	-6.805***	I(1)

Notes: 1) *denotes significance level at 5% and 10%; **denotes significance level at 10% While ***denotes significance level at 1%, 5% and 10%.

2) The test statistics value of PP test is based on Spectral estimation method-Bartlett Kernel and the Bandwidth is New-West Bandwidth automatic selection by the software itself.

A5. Johansen Jusilius test:**Table 4: Appendix to Section 5.3 Johansen Jusilius test:**

Trend: constant; Number of observation = 30

Sample: 1982 – 2011; Lags = 2

vecrank lngdp lnX lnM, trend(constant) max levela

JOHANSEN AND JUSELIUS COINTEGRATION RESULT

Hypothesis	λ_{max}				λ_{trace}			
	r=0	r≤ 1	r≤ 2	r≤ 3	r=0	r≤ 1	r≤ 2	r≤ 3
Null								
Alternative	r=1	r=2	r=3	r=4	r=1	r=2	r=3	r=4
5% critical value	(20.97)	(14.07)	(3.76)	(9.19)	(29.68)	(15.41)	(3.76)	(10.02)
	19.8411*	8.3272*	1.6195*	7.416*	28.7877*	9.9467*	1.6195*	8.361
1% critical value	(25.52)	(18.63)	(6.65)	(12.09)	(35.65)	(20.04)	(6.65)	(15.39)

Notes: (i) r = number of cointegrating vectors; (ii) The lag order for each VAR is chosen by AIC as shown in parenthesis; (iii) * denote acceptance of the null hypothesis at the 5% and 1% significance level respectively meaning no cointegration i.e. no long run relation. (iii) The numbers in bold format are the calculated value of λ_{max} and Trace statistics (λ_{trace}) respectively

A6. Granger causality test:**Table 5: Appendix to Section 5.4****Causality between GDP and Export:**

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Probability	Decision
LNX does not Granger Cause LNGDP	31	23.8291	3.8E-05	Reject
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNX		3.18527	0.08514	Reject
Lags: 2				
LNX does not Granger Cause LNGDP	30	7.03659	0.00377	Reject
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNX		3.75362	0.03754	Reject
Lags: 3				
LNX does not Granger Cause LNGDP	29	3.58403	0.03006	Reject
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNX		1.69455	0.19731	Do not Reject
Lags: 4				
LNX does not Granger Cause LNGDP	28	3.92485	0.01735	Reject
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNX		1.41389	0.26747	Do not Reject
Lags: 5				
LNX does not Granger Cause LNGDP	27	5.83853	0.00296	Reject
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNX		1.62788	0.20934	Do not reject
Lags: 6				
LNX does not Granger Cause LNGDP	26	6.15914	0.00303	Reject
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNX		0.83838	0.56195	Do not reject
Lags: 7				
LNX does not Granger Cause LNGDP	25	3.89454	0.02613	Reject
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNX		1.56636	0.25069	Do not reject
Lags: 8				
LNX does not Granger Cause LNGDP	24	2.3850	0.22699	Do not reject
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNX		2.87710	0.43143	Do not reject

Causality between GDP and FDI:

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Sample: 1980 2011

Lags: 1

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Probability	Decision
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNFDI	31	7.09199	0.01269	Reject
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNGDP		6.80685	0.01441	Reject
Lags: 2				
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNFDI	30	4.42882	0.02257	Reject
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNGDP		2.08323	0.14561	Do not Reject
Lags: 3				
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNFDI	29	3.98722	0.02074	Reject
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNGDP		1.21852	0.32648	Do not Reject
Lags: 4				
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNFDI	28	1.02073	0.00179	Reject
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNGDP		1.47766	0.24828	Do not Reject
Lags: 5				
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNFDI	27	0.92945	0.08775	Reject
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNGDP		0.83543	0.54353	Do not Reject
Lags: 6				
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNFDI	26	2.40052	0.00754	Reject
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNGDP		0.64749	0.69192	Do not Reject
Lags: 7				
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNFDI	25	2.23546	0.00123	Reject
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNGDP		0.42327	0.86685	Do not Reject
Lags: 8				
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNFDI	24	2.21146	0.22010	Do not Reject
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNGDP		0.31127	0.75515	Do not Reject

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